

Stereoselective and Simple Syntheses of Gossyplure, *Pectinophora gossypiella*

O. P. VIG, M. L. SHARMA*, ARUN SABHARWAL, SANJIV SHARMA, RASHMI GUPTA and VIJAY DOGRA

Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh-160 014

Manuscript received 3 February 1989, accepted 23 May 1989

Through an unambiguous route based on the application of dilithium tetrachlorocuprate catalysed coupling reaction, syntheses of (7*Z*, 11*Z*)- and (7*Z*, 11*E*)-7,11-hexadecadien-1-yl acetates, the pheromone components of *Pectinophora gossypiella*, have been reported.

THE pink bollworm moth, *Pectinophora gossypiella* is one of the most destructive pests to cotton crops. The sex pheromone released by the female pink bollworm moth was identified as 1 : 1 mixture of (7*Z*, 11*Z*)- and (7*Z*, 11*E*)-7,11-hexadecadien-1-yl acetates and this mixture was given the name gossyplure¹⁻³. The synthetic mixture was found to be highly attractive to male moths in field-tests^{1,2}. (7*Z*, 11*Z*)- and (7*Z*, 11*E*)-7,11-hexadecadien-1-yl acetates have been identified as sex pheromone components of other insect species as well⁴⁻⁶.

Many syntheses of these pheromones are reported in the literature⁷⁻¹⁰. We report here another synthesis of the title compounds through an unambiguous route (Scheme 1).

3(*E*)-Octenoic acid¹¹ on treatment with ethyl chloroformate/Et₃N¹² in anhydrous dichloromethane afforded the anhydride (3). Reduction of 3 with NaBH₄ in ethanol followed by bromination with PBr₃/Py yielded the bromide (5). On the other hand, oct-3-yn-1-ol (6) was prepared by alkylation of dilithio derivative of 3-butyn-1-ol with 1-bromobutane in the presence of Li/Liq.NH₃ using ferric nitrate as catalyst and THF as cosolvent. 6 was partially hydrogenated over Lindlar's catalyst and the reduced alcohol was converted into the corresponding bromide (7) by using PBr₃/Py as usual. Bromides 5 and 7 were treated with 3-tetrahydropyranyloxypropynylmagnesium bromide in presence of cuprous chloride¹³ in dry THF under N₂ atmosphere to get 8 and 9. Depyration, partial hydrogenation followed by bromination of 8 and 9 yielded 12 and 13 which were coupled with 5-bromo-1-tetrahydropyranyloxy-pentane in presence of Li₂CuCl₄ as a catalyst to afford 14 and 15. Acetylation of 14 and 15 with AcCl/AcOH gave the title pheromones 1 and 2. The spectral data of synthetic 1 and 2 was in agreement with those reported in literature⁷⁻¹⁰.

Scheme 1

Experimental

IR spectra (film) of compounds were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CCl₄) on a Varian EM-390 spectrophotometer using TMS as an internal standard. Silica gel (ASC, Bombay) impregnated with CaSO₄ was used for tlc. Unless otherwise stated, all the organic extracts were dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate.

5(*E*)-Octenoic-ethanoic anhydride (3) : To an ice-cooled solution of 3(*E*)-octenoic acid (14.2 g, 100 mmol) and triethylamine (15.15 g, 150 mmol) in dry CH₂Cl₂ (50 ml), ethyl chloroformate (16.2 g,

150 mmol) was added dropwise at 0° and stirred further for 4 h (tlc monitoring). The reaction mixture was then washed with water (2×100 ml), extracted with dichloromethane and dried. Evaporation of the solvent followed by column chromatography of the crude material furnished 3 (12.9 g, 69%) (Found: C, 61.52; H, 8.33. $C_{11}H_{18}O_4$ requires: C, 61.68; H, 8.41%); ν_{max} 2 920, 1 740, 1 650 and 970 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.9 (6H, m), 1.3–1.6 (4H, m), 2.0–2.2 (2H, m), 3.0 (2H, d), 4.1 (2H, q) and 5.6–5.8 (2H, m).

3(E)-Octen-1-ol (4): To a well-stirred slurry of $NaBH_4$ (4.11 g, 128 mmol) in ethanol (50 ml) was added the anhydride (3; 12 g, 64 mmol) during 1 h. The reaction mixture was then further stirred for 3 h and acidified with dilute acetic acid till effervescence ceased. Ethanol was evaporated, the residue extracted with ether (4×50 ml), washed with aqueous $NaHCO_3$ solution and brine and dried. Removal of solvent followed by column chromatography over silica gel using petroleum ether as eluent gave 4 (5.58 g, 68%) (Found: C, 74.86; H, 12.62. $C_8H_{16}O$ requires: C, 75.00; H, 12.5%); ν_{max} 3 500–3 300b, 2 900, 1 650, 1 475 and 970 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.9 (3H, t), 1.2–1.5 (4H, m), 2.0–2.3 (4H, m), 4.0 (2H, m), 4.7 (1H, s) and 5.4–5.6 (2H, m).

1-Bromo-3(E)-octene (5): Freshly distilled PBr_3 (2.67 ml, 28 mmol) in dry ether (15 ml) was added to the alcohol (4; 5.58 g, 44 mmol) in dry ether (100 ml) containing a small amount of pyridine and allowed to stand overnight. The resulting solution was refluxed for 2 h, cooled, poured into ice-cooled water and extracted with ether (4×50 ml). The ethereal extract was washed with 10% aqueous $NaHCO_3$ and brine and dried. Evaporation of solvent furnished 5 (5.66 g, 68%). The absence of ir absorption at 3 500–3 300 cm^{-1} confirmed the formation of the bromide (5).

3-Octyn-1-ol (6): To well-stirred liquid ammonia (1 dm³) containing catalytic amount of $Fe(NO_3)_3$ was slowly added Li-metal (2.1 g). After blue colour had disappeared, 3-butyn-1-ol (7.0 g) in dry THF (20 ml) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h and then 1-bromobutane (13.7 g) in dry THF (20 ml) was added to it dropwise and stirred for further 3 h. The reaction was quenched with NH_4Cl , ammonia allowed to evaporate and the residue extracted with ether (4×50 ml), washed with brine and dried. The solvent was evaporated and the crude material purified through column chromatography over silica gel using petroleum ether–ether (9:1) as eluent to afford 6 (7.83 g, 62.2%) (Found: C, 75.98; H, 11.05. $C_8H_{14}O$ requires: C, 76.19; H, 11.11%); ν_{max} 3 450, 2 870, 2 300, 2 220, 2 190, 1 440 and 1 050 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.95 (3H, t), 1.45 (4H, m), 2.1–2.3 (4H, m) and 3.90 (3H, t).

1-Bromo-(Z)-3-octene (7): The acetylenic alcohol (6; 7.5 g, 60 mmol) was hydrogenated in presence of Lindlar's catalyst (500 mg) and quinoline (2 drops) using dry hexane (25 ml) as solvent. When one

equivalent of hydrogen was taken up, the catalyst was filtered off. The solution was washed with dilute acetic acid and water and dried. Solvent removal followed by chromatography of the residue over silica gel gave tlc-pure 3(Z)-octen-1-ol (6.8 g, 90%) (Found: C, 74.82; H, 12.28. $C_8H_{16}O$ requires: C, 75.00; H, 12.50%); ν_{max} 3 390, 2 940, 2 880, 1 650, 1 460, 1 220, 1 040 and 725 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.9 (3H, t), 1.2–1.45 (4H, bs), 2.2–2.35 (4H, m), 3.8 (2H, t), 4.1 (1H, bs) and 5.5 (2H, m). Phosphoroustribromide (2.4 ml) in dry ether (10 ml) was added to 3(Z)-octen-1-ol (6.5 g) in dry ether (100 ml) containing pyridine (3–4 drops) and allowed to stand overnight. After refluxing for 2 h, the reaction mixture was cooled, poured into ice-cold water, extracted with ether (4×50 ml), washed with 10% aqueous $NaHCO_3$ solution and brine and dried. Removal of solvent furnished 7 (7.7 g, 80%). Its ir spectrum showed complete absence of absorption bands in the hydroxyl region.

1-Tetrahydropyranyloxy-undec-6(E)-en-2-yne (8) and 1-tetrahydropyranyloxy-undec-6(Z)-en-2-yne (9): To a well-stirred solution of ethylmagnesiumbromide (prepared from 10.9 g of ethyl bromide and 2.4 g of Mg turnings in 15 ml anhydrous THF), 3-tetrahydropyranyloxyprop-1-yne (14 g, 100 mmol) dissolved in dry THF (20 ml) was added during 30 min period and the reaction mixture was gently refluxed for 6 h (40–50°). The contents were cooled to room temperature and cuprous chloride (0.5 g) was added to the mixture rapidly, stirred for 15 min and 3(E)-octenyl bromide (19.1 g, 100 mmol)/3(Z)-octenyl bromide (19.1 g, 100 mmol) in dry THF (20 ml) was added during 20 min. The reaction was quenched with saturated NH_4Cl solution, extracted with ether (4×50 ml), washed with brine and dried. Removal of solvent followed by chromatography over silica gel using petroleum ether–ether (9:1) as eluent afforded 8 (13.25 g, 53%)/9 (13.12 g, 52.5%): 8 (Found: C, 76.66; H, 10.29. $C_{16}H_{26}O_2$ requires: C, 76.80; H, 10.40%); ν_{max} 2 950, 2 250, 1 650, 980, 890, 870 and 810 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.9 (3H, t), 1.2–1.6 (10H, m), 2.0–2.3 (6H, m), 3.8 (2H, m), 4.1 (2H, s), 4.6 (1H, s) and 5.4–5.6 (2H, m); 9 (Found: C, 6.68; H, 10.36. $C_{16}H_{26}O_2$ requires: C, 76.80; H, 10.40%); ν_{max} 3 010, 2 800, 2 320, 2 250, 1 640, 1 450, 1 220, 890, 870, 810 and 710 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.88 (3H, t), 1.25–1.67 (10H, bs), 1.9–2.4 (4H, m), 3.0 (2H, m), 3.8 (2H, m), 4.2 (2H, s), 4.8 (1H, s) and 5.3–5.4 (2H, m).

6(E)-Undecen-2-yn-1-ol (10) and 6(Z)-undecen-2-yn-1-ol (11): A solution of 8 (12.5 g, 50 mmol)/9 (12.5 g, 50 mmol) and PTS (0.850 g) in methanol (50 ml) was stirred for 6 h at 55°, cooled and neutralised with solid $NaHCO_3$. Methanol was removed under reduced pressure to afford a residue which was diluted with water, extracted with ether (3×25 ml) and dried. The solvent was evaporated and the residue chromatographed over silica gel using petroleum ether–ether (9:1) as eluent to give 10 (4.81 g, 58%)/11 (4.81 g, 58.1%): 10 (Found:

C, 79.41; H, 10.71. $C_{11}H_{18}O$ requires: C, 79.50; H, 10.84%; ν_{\max} 3 500–3 200, 2 950, 2 200, 1 650, 1 450 and 980 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.9 (3H, t), 1.2–1.4 (4H, m), 1.9–2.2 (6H, m), 3.6 (1H, s), 4.1 (2H, s) and 5.5–5.8 (2H, m); **11** (Found: C, 79.36; H, 10.68. $C_{11}H_{18}O$ requires: C, 79.50; H, 10.84%; ν_{\max} 3 400–3 320, 2 970, 2 240, 2 190, 1 650, 1 460, 1 220, 1 040, 730 and 705 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.88 (3H, t), 1.20–1.52 (4H, bs), 2.0–2.2 (4H, m), 3.0 (2H, m), 3.52 (1H, bs), 4.2 (2H, t) and 5.32 (2H, m).

1-Bromo-(2Z, 6E)-2,6-undecadiene (12) and 1-bromo-(2Z, 6Z)-2,6-undecadiene (13): The alcohol (**10**; 4.0 g, 24 mmol/**11**; 4.0 g, 24 mmol) was hydrogenated in presence of Lindlar's catalyst (400 mg) and quinoline (2–3 drops) in dry hexane followed by bromination of the reduced alcohols (3.5 g) with PBr_3/Py (1.1 ml) using the procedure reported for **7** to afford the bromide (**12**; 3.69 g, 75%/13; 3.64 g, 74%) which was used as such for the next reactions.

1-Tetrahydropyranyloxy-(7Z, 11E)-7,11-hexadecadiene (14) and 1-tetrahydropyranyloxy-(7Z, 11Z)-7,11-hexadecadiene (15): To the Grignard reagent (prepared from 5-bromo-1-tetrahydropyranyloxypentane (2.51 g, 10 mmol) and activated Mg turnings (0.24 g, 10 mmol) in dry THF (15 ml) under N_2 -atmosphere), was added the bromide (**12**; 2.31 g, 10 mmol/15, 2.31 g, 10 mmol) in anhydrous THF (5 ml) dropwise at -10° and stirred for 30 min. To the resulting mixture, a catalytic amount of Li_2CuCl_4 (1.5 ml) was added and stirred for 5 h at -10° . The reaction was quenched with saturated NH_4Cl solution, extracted with ether (4×40 ml), washed with brine and dried. Removal of the solvent followed by chromatography over silica gel employing petroleum ether–ether (9 : 1) as eluent, gave **14** (1.61 g, 50%)/**15** (1.64 g, 51%): **14** (Found: C, 78.11; H, 11.69. $C_{21}H_{38}O_2$ requires: C, 78.26; H, 11.80%; ν_{\max} 2 950, 1 650, 1 450, 980, 890, 815 and 725 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.9 (3H, t), 1.3–1.7 (20H, m), 2.1–2.5 (8H, m), 3.5–3.8 (4H, m), 4.6 (1H, s), 5.3–5.6 (2H, m, J 5 Hz) and 5.65–5.9 (2H, d, J 15 Hz); **15** (Found: C, 78.15; H, 11.62. $C_{21}H_{38}O_2$ requires: C, 78.26; H, 11.80%; ν_{\max} 2 925, 2 860, 1 640, 1 460, 1 240, 910, 895, 815 and 710 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.95 (3H, t), 1.2–1.7 (18H, bs), 2.0 (8H, m), 3.25–3.85 (4H, m), 4.58 (1H, s) and 5.2–5.52 (4H, m).

(7Z, 11E)-7,11-Hexadecadien-1-yl acetate (1) and (7Z, 11Z)-7,11-hexadecadien-1-yl acetate (2): A mixture of acetyl chloride (0.7 ml, 10 mmol), acetic

acid (2 ml, 35 mmol) and pyridine (0.8 ml, 10 mmol) was added to **14** (1.61 g, 5 mmol)/**15** (1.61 g, 5 mmol) at 0° dropwise during 1 h and stirred for 12 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was decomposed with cold water, extracted with ether, washed with 5% $NaHCO_3$ solution and dried. The solvent was removed and the resulting solution was chromatographed over silica gel using petroleum ether–ether (9 : 1) to give **1** (1.12 g, 80%)/**2** (1.09 g, 78%): **1** (Found: C, 76.99; H, 11.31. $C_{18}H_{32}O_2$ requires: C, 77.14; H, 11.42%; ν_{\max} 2 950, 1 745, 1 660, 980 and 730 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.9 (3H, t), 1.1–1.4 (12H, m), 1.8–2.0 (8H, m), 2.1 (3H, s), 4.0 (2H, t), 5.3–5.6 (2H, m, J 5 Hz) and 5.65–5.9 (2H, d, J 15 Hz); **2** (Found: C, 77.05; H, 11.28. $C_{18}H_{32}O_2$ requires: C, 77.14; H, 11.42%; ν_{\max} 3 000, 2 925, 2 865, 1 730, 1 640, 1 460, 1 360, 1 220, 1 030 and 720 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.93 (3H, t), 1.1–1.6 (12H, m), 1.70–2.22 (11H, m), 4.1 (2H, t) and 5.2–5.5 (4H, m).

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for financial support.

References

1. H. E. HUMMEL, L. K. GASTON, H. H. SHORRY, R. S. KAAE, K. J. BYRNE and R. M. SILVERSTEIN, *Science*, 1973, 181, 878.
2. B. A. BIERL, M. BEROZA, R. T. STATEN, P. E. SONNET and V. E. ADLER, *J. Econ. Entomol.*, 1974, 67, 211.
3. H. M. FLINT, M. BALASUBRAMANIAN, J. CAMPERO, G. R. STRICKLAND, Z. AHMED, J. BARRAL, S. BARBOSA and A. F. KHAIL, *J. Econ. Entomol.*, 1979, 72, 758.
4. G. H. L. ROTHSCHILD, *Environ. Entomol.*, 1975, 4, 983.
5. K. W. WICK, *Experientia*, 1974, 30, 17.
6. D. L. STRUBLE, G. E. SWAILS and G. L. AYRE, *Can. Entomol.*, 1977, 109, 975.
7. T. ISHIIHARA and A. YAMAMOTO, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1984, 48, 211.
8. J. M. MUCHOWSKI and M. O. VENUTI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1981, 46, 459.
9. K. HAMMOUDAN and O. DESCOINS, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1978, 2, 299.
10. I. ANDELIC, F. MYHREN and L. SKATTEBOL, *Acta Chem. Scand., Ser. B*, 1985, 39, 281.
11. R. NIKITAR, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1987, 28, 93.
12. *Org. Synth.*, 1963, 4, 285.
13. S. O. JAIN, D. E. DUSSOURD, W. E. CONNER, T. EISNER, A. GUERRERO and J. MEINWALD, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1983, 48, 2266.